

HPO terms related to glycobiology terms, searched with Protégé*

Categories	HPO terms	HPO Identifiers
Abnormal glucose homeostasis	Abnormal glucose homeostasis	HP:0011014
	Abnormal blood glucose concentration	HP:0011015
	Hyperglycemia	HP:0003074
	Postprandial hyperglycemia	HP:0011998
	Hypoglycemia	HP:0001943
	Hypoglycemic seizures	HP:0002173
	Hypoketotic hypoglycemia	HP:0001985
	Ketotic hypoglycemia	HP:0012734
	Neonatal hypoglycemia	HP:0001998
	Nonketotic hypoglycemia	HP:0001958
	Reactive hypoglycemia	HP:0012051
	Recurrent hypoglycemia	HP:0001988
	Recurrent infantile hypoglycemia	HP:0004914
	Glucose intolerance	HP:0001952
	Diabetes mellitus	HP:0000819
	Diabetic ketoacidosis	HP:0001953
	Insulin-resistant diabetes mellitus	HP:0000831
	Insulin-resistant diabetes mellitus at puberty	HP:0000877
	Neonatal insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus	HP:0000857
	Transient neonatal diabetes mellitus	HP:0008255
	Maternal diabetes	HP:0009800
	Maturity-onset diabetes of the young	HP:0004904
	Type I diabetes mellitus	HP:0100651
	Type II diabetes mellitus	HP:0005978
	Insulin-dependent but ketosis-resistant diabetes	HP:0008205
	Impaired glucose tolerance	HP:0040270
	Abnormal oral glucose tolerance	HP:0004924

Hyperinsulinemia	HP:0000842
Fasting hyperinsulinemia	HP:0008283
Hyperinsulinemic hypoglycemia	HP:0000825
Impaired gluconeogenesis	HP:0005959
Increased proinsulin:insulin ratio	HP:0031883
Insulin insensitivity	HP:0008189
Insulin resistance	HP:0000855
Insulin-resistant diabetes mellitus	HP:0000831
Insulin-resistant diabetes mellitus at puberty	HP:0000877
Neonatal insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus	HP:0000857
Transient neonatal diabetes mellitus	HP:0008255
Abnormal glycosylation	HP:0012345
Abnormality of glycolipid metabolism	HP:0010969
Abnormality of glycosphingolipid metabolism	HP:0004343
Abnormality of cerebroside metabolism	HP:0004344
Absence of ganglioside GM3	HP:0410370
Ganglioside accumulation	HP:0004345
GM2-ganglioside accumulation	HP:0003495
Increased globoside Gb3 level	HP:0410368
Increased globoside Gb4 level	HP:0410366
Abnormal protein glycosylation	HP:0012346
Abnormal protein N-linked glycosylation	HP:0012347
Abnormal complex N-glycan level	HP:0410351
Decreased complex N-glycan level	HP:0410353
Increased complex N-glycan level	HP:0410352
Abnormal fucosylation of protein N-linked glycosylation	HP:0012352
Decreased fucosylation of N-linked protein glycosylation	HP:0012353
Increased fucosylation of N-linked protein glycosylation	HP:0012354
Abnormal high-mannose N-glycan level	HP:0410356
Decreased high-mannose N-glycan level	HP:0410358
Increased high-mannose N-glycan level	HP:0410357

**Abnormal glycosylation
(abnormality of glycolipid metabolism
and abnormal protein glycosylation)**

Abnormal isoelectric focusing of serum transferrin	HP:0003160	
Type I transferrin isoform profile	HP:0003642	
Type II transferrin isoform profile	HP:0012301	
Abnormal mannosylation of N-linked protein glycosylation	HP:0012355	
Decreased mannosylation of N-linked protein glycosylation	HP:0012356	
Increased mannosylation of N-linked protein glycosylation	HP:0012357	
Abnormal sialylation of N-linked protein glycosylation	HP:0012349	
Decreased sialylated N-glycan level	HP:0410355	
Decreased sialylation of N-linked protein glycosylation	HP:0012350	
Increased sialylated N-glycan level	HP:0410354	
Increased sialylation of N-linked protein glycosylation	HP:0012351	
Decreased galactosylation of N-linked protein glycosylation	HP:0012348	
Abnormal protein O-linked glycosylation	HP:0012358	
Abnormal core 1 O-glycan level	HP:0410359	
Decreased core 1 O-glycan level	HP:0410361	
Increased core 1 O-glycan level	HP:0410360	
Abnormal fucosylation of O-linked protein glycosylation	HP:0012359	
Decreased fucosylation of O-linked protein glycosylation	HP:0012360	
Increased fucosylation of O-linked protein glycosylation	HP:0012361	
Shortened O-fucosylated glycan on properdin	HP:0410344	
Abnormal sialylation of O-linked protein glycosylation	HP:0012362	
Decreased monosialylated core 1 O-glycan level	HP:0410364	
Decreased sialylation of O-linked protein glycosylation	HP:0012363	
Increased disialylated core 1 O-glycan level	HP:0410365	
Increased monosialylated core 1 O-glycan level	HP:0410363	
Increased Tn-antigen level	HP:0410372	
Abnormal glycosyltransferase activity	Decreased beta-glucocerebrosidase activity	HP:0003656
	Decreased glucosephosphate isomerase activity	HP:0003568
	Decreased glycosyltransferase O-Fucosylpeptide 3-Beta-N-Acetylglucosaminyltransferase activity	HP:0410349
	Reduced activity of N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase II	HP:0003655

Abnormal free glycans level

Abnormal circulating carbohydrate concentration	HP:0011013
Abnormal circulating glycerol level	HP:0031795
Decreased circulating glycerol level	HP:0031794
Hyperglycerolemia	HP:0040302
Abnormal circulating heparan sulfate level	HP:0410341
Decreased circulating heparan sulfate level	HP:0410343
Increased circulating heparan sulfate level	HP:0410342
Abnormal circulating polysaccharide concentration	HP:0011012
Abnormal circulating hyaluronic acid concentration	HP:0031210
Abnormality of glycolysis	HP:0004366
Increased serum pyruvate	HP:0003542
Decreased level of 1,5 anhydroglucitol in serum	HP:0410050
Elevated cancer Ag 19-9 level	HP:0032345
Elevated circulating ribitol concentration	HP:0025550
Hypergalactosemia	HP:0012024
Increased level of D-threitol in plasma	HP:0410057
Increased level of galactitol in plasma	HP:0410061
Increased level of galactitol in red blood cells	HP:0410064
Abnormal urine carbohydrate level	HP:0031979
Decreased level of D-mannose in urine	HP:0410060
Decreased level of erythritol in urine	HP:0410055
Galactosuria	HP:0012023
Increased level of D-threitol in urine	HP:0410059
Increased level of galactitol in urine	HP:0410062
Increased level of L-fucose in urine	HP:0410067
Increased level of ribitol in urine	HP:0410070
Increased level of ribose in urine	HP:0410072
Increased level of xylitol in urine	HP:0410074
Increased urinary glycerol	HP:0040301
Increased urinary sedoheptulose	HP:0025157
Oligosacchariduria	HP:0010471

Increased urinary disaccharide excretion	HP:0012066
Increased urinary fucosylated oligosaccharide	HP:0410350
Increased urinary galactosylated oligosaccharide	HP:0410346
Increased urinary high-mannose-type oligosaccharide	HP:0410347
Increased urinary multiantennary sialylated oligosaccharide	HP:0410348
Increased urinary polyhexose	HP:0410345
Urinary excretion of sialylated oligosaccharides	HP:0012061

Legend

*Search from HPO
version updated from Github
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Glycobiology terms:

glycan, sugar, carbohydrate, glycoproteins,
glycolipid, glycosyltransferase, lectin